

Coeducational education and gender gaps: Evidence from School Transitions

Jaime Polanco¹, Gloria Bernal² & Kristof De Witte^{1,3}

1. LEER, Faculty of Economics and Business, KU Leuven, Belgium
2. Department of Economics, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana, Colombia

Summary

1. Boys consistently underperform in education, with lower academic achievement (especially in reading), higher grade repetition, early school leaving, and lower tertiary enrollment across many countries.
2. Quasi-experimental evidence suggests that converting male-only schools to coeducation leads to significant declines in boys' mathematics (-0.54 SD) performance, even when peer composition changes are relatively small. While coeducation increases overall female STEM enrollment (+6.43 percentage points), it triggers a "vertical sorting" effect, shifting participation toward vocational tracks rather than four-year university programs.
3. These findings indicate that without accompanying pedagogical adaptations, coeducation may come at the cost of unintended long-term economic and educational externalities.

1. Introduction and Policy Motivation

The organization of schooling based on gender remains a subject of significant debate across educational jurisdictions. In both Latin American and European contexts, systems have largely trended toward coeducation. This shift is frequently motivated by two factors: the sociopolitical goal of promoting gender equality and the economic imperative of administrative efficiency. Managing a unified, coeducational system is logistically less complex than maintaining segregated facilities.

However, the widespread assumption that coeducation is neutral – or uniformly beneficial – for learning outcomes warrants closer examination. Across many education systems, boys experience persistently weaker educational trajectories, reflected in higher dropout rates and uneven academic performance; in the EU, for example, 10.9% of young men were early school leavers in 2024, compared with 7.7% of young women. Substantial gender gaps are also evident in international assessments. Data from PISA 2022 show that across OECD countries, boys outperform girls in mathematics by an average of nine points, while girls outperform boys in reading by approximately 24 points;

in science, average performance does not differ meaningfully by gender. These disparities are especially pronounced at the lower end of the achievement distribution, where boys are significantly more likely than girls to be low performers in reading (31% versus 22%), whereas rates of low performance in mathematics are nearly identical for boys (31%) and girls (32%). At the top of the distribution, boys are more strongly represented among high achievers in mathematics (11% compared with 7% of girls), while girls are slightly more prevalent among top performers in reading (8% versus 6%), with gender differences in science remaining modest at both the lower and upper ends.

It might be questioned whether coeducational environments interact with gender-specific learning dynamics in ways that disadvantage male engagement, particularly in literacy and school persistence.

This policy brief summarizes recent causal evidence derived from large-scale school conversions in Colombia, providing a unique window into these dynamics (Bernal & De Witte, 2026; Polanco-Jiménez, De Witte & Bernal, 2026). Because these conversions were driven by logistical capacity constraints rather than pedagogical strategies, they offer a natural experiment that mitigates many of the selection issues common in comparisons between single-sex and coeducational schools (Pahlke et al., 2014). While the evidence comes from Colombia, the question and female-male interaction are common though undergoing similar transitions in Europe and elsewhere.

2. Behavioral Economic Mechanisms

The interaction between coeducational environments and gender-specific learning dynamics is driven by a range of socio-behavioral and academic mechanisms that influence human capital formation. If coeducational environments interact with gender-specific learning dynamics, these interactions function through four primary channels identified in the literature, spanning classroom behavior, institutional expectations, and individual decision-making.

2.1 Peer Effects and Behavioral Dynamics

Classroom gender composition fundamentally alters the learning environment. Evidence suggests that male-only environments foster specific learning dynamics often characterized by higher competitiveness. The disruption of this environment by the introduction of the opposite sex appears to have asymmetric effects. For boys, the presence of girls can lead to distraction or less disciplined behavior, negatively impacting academic focus (Dustmann et al., 2018). For girls, the presence of boys alters the reference group for academic comparison, shifting the competitive landscape (Loyalka et al., 2017; Polanco-Jiménez et al., 2026).

2.2 Teacher–Student Interactions and Behavioral Expectations

Beyond peer effects, teacher–student interactions also shape gender-differentiated outcomes in coeducational settings. Teachers’ expectations and disciplinary practices vary systematically by gender, with boys more likely to face sanctions and lower evaluations of noncognitive skills, even conditional on

achievement (Cornwell et al., 2013; Lavy & Sand, 2018). These patterns may amplify gender gaps in engagement, particularly for boys, while role-model effects and teacher interactions play a more limited, though still relevant, role for girls' engagement and subject choice (Carlana, 2019).

2.3 Norms and Stereotype Threat

Coeducation exposes students to cross-gender social norms. This acts as a normalizing mechanism, effectively lowering the psychological barriers for women to enter "male" fields (Lavy & Schlosser, 2011). Conversely, when stereotypes become salient, especially in evaluative or high-pressure contexts, stereotype threat can undermine performance and confidence, with particularly well-documented negative effects for girls and women in mathematics (Steele & Aronson, 1995; Spencer et al., 2016). The interaction of these forces determines whether a student pursues a high-status career or retreats to a lower-tier qualification. Math confidence and achievement are closely linked to later course-taking and STEM entry (Wang & Degol, 2017).

2.4 Comparative Advantage and the "Vertical Trade-off"

In coeducational settings, expanded peer comparisons can weaken female students' academic confidence, particularly when male peers display higher competitiveness. This may reduce classroom engagement and self-perception—key inputs into academic performance—without necessarily reflecting differences in underlying ability (Niederle & Vesterlund, 2011). Over time, diminished self-perception can shift educational aspirations away from competitive university STEM programs toward vocational or technical tracks—a “vertical trade-off” driven by

perceived rather than actual ability (Loyalka et al., 2017).

3. Methodology and Data

Both studies evaluate the same policy change: public single-sex schools (either all-boys or all-girls) transitioning to mixed-gender coeducation. To measure the impact of this change, we use a research design that compares schools that transitioned in different years against similar schools that remained single-sex during the same period. Because these transitions were rolled out gradually over time for purely administrative reasons—such as municipal capacity optimization rather than school performance—they provide a natural experiment.

This allows us to compare students before and after the transition and isolate the true causal effect of coeducation from other factors. The two papers evaluate different timeframes and student outcomes. While Bernal & De Witte (2026) analyze test performance on Colombia's standardized high school exit examination (Saber 11) from 2001 to 2019, focusing on schools with cohorts of at least 30 students, Polanco-Jiménez et al. (2026) study the 2013 to 2019 period and link high school records to national higher education registries. This linkage allows us to track long-term outcomes, such as college enrollment and specific field-of-study choices, including STEM fields.

4. Review of Empirical Evidence

4.1 Impact on Academic Performance

The transition to coeducation can generate a negative externality for boys' human capital

accumulation. By comparing schools that transitioned to coeducation in different years, Bernal and De Witte (2026) find that incumbent boys experience meaningful declines in test performance after girls enter (about -0.54 SD in mathematics). This decline is attributed to peer effects rather than changes in school quality, supporting the hypothesis that boys experience reduced competitiveness or loss of focus in mixed environments. These results are in line with those from South Korea—one of the few other settings where the shift between single-sex and coeducational schooling has been evaluated with credible causal designs (Park, Behrman, & Choi, 2013). For female students, the estimated effects on incumbent girls in converting female-only schools are not statistically distinguishable from zero.

4.2 The Horizontal-Vertical Trade-off in Schooling Decisions

Next, we study the impact of coeducation on post-secondary choices. The data reveals a distinct trade-off. On the horizontal margin, coeducation is a success: transitioning to a coeducational setting significantly increases the probability of female students choosing STEM majors by approximately 6.43 percentage points (Polanco-Jiménez et al., 2026). This suggests that exposure to male peers effectively lowers the barriers to entry for women in traditionally male-dominated fields.

However, on the vertical margin, this success is tempered by a reallocation within STEM pathways rather than an overall retreat from higher education. In Polanco-Jiménez et al. (2026), the rise in STEM participation is driven primarily by enrollment in shorter-cycle vocational and technical programs, while enrollment in four-year university bachelor's STEM degrees declines by

approximately 6 percentage points. This phenomenon, characterized as 'vertical sorting,' is highly compatible with broader patterns documented in Europe. In the EU, as in Colombia, women are more likely than men to complete tertiary education overall (exceeding 50% enrollment), yet they remain underrepresented in high-stakes STEM credentials—accounting for only about 32.8% of tertiary STEM graduates. The evidence suggests that while coeducation successfully lowers entry barriers to male-dominated fields, it may inadvertently shift the level of credential chosen, likely due to intensified peer competition and comparative advantage assessments (Böheim et al., 2017; Loyalka et al., 2017).

Notably, these vertical sorting effects compound over time, indicating that prolonged exposure to a coeducational environment increases the shift away from university STEM programs.

Validation via Asymmetry

The direction of the transition validates these behavioral mechanisms. Evidence from schools transitioning from male-only to coeducational shows a starkly different pattern for the minority of incoming girls. For these students, entering a historically male environment results in a decrease in STEM major selection. This asymmetry confirms that "coeducation" is not a uniform treatment; the incumbent culture matters. When women enter a male-dominated culture without critical mass, stereotype threat discourages participation. Conversely, when men enter female-dominated schools, they disrupt norms enough to encourage female STEM entry (horizontal gain) but deter high-stakes competition (vertical loss).

< Figure 1 about here >

5. Review of Empirical Evidence

The evidence indicates that the choice for coeducation can have far-reaching consequences. While the empirical analysis draws on data from Colombia, its causal design and rich data offer valuable insights into how peer composition and learning environments shape educational outcomes. Based on the results, we suggest the following policy implications.

First, the observed decline in male performance indicates that mixing genders needs pedagogical adjustment. Schools transitioning to or operating as coeducational institutions should implement targeted behavioral and instructional strategies to maintain the academic focus of male students and mitigate average gender-differentiated patterns of classroom disruption (behaviors more frequently observed among boys in many settings) that can generate negative spillovers on peer learning for both boys and girls. Teacher training programs must be updated to equip educators with strategies for managing the more complex behavioral dynamics of mixed classrooms, so coeducation does not come at the cost of learning outcomes.

Second, because the transition from single-sex schooling to coeducation can generate heterogeneous effects, most clearly a decline in boys' achievement and, for girls, shifts in postsecondary pathways, educational planners might consider hybrid implementation models at the high-school level. Rather than a binary choice between segregation and total integration, schools could pilot retaining single-sex classes for specific subjects, such as mathematics or science, within a coeducational school

framework (Eisenkopf et al., 2015). This approach could preserve the benefits of reduced distraction for boys and reduced stereotype threat for girls while maintaining the social and administrative benefits of a mixed school environment.

What is BRIDGE?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

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Figures

THE COEDUCATION TRADE-OFF: IMPACTS ON PERFORMANCE & PATHWAYS

Figure 1

Further Information:

Polanco-Jiménez, J., De Witte, K., & Bernal, G. L. (2026). Does Coeducation Close the STEM Gap? Evidence from a Single-Sex Schooling Transition in Colombia. *Leuven Economics of Education Research (KU Leuven) & Pontificia Universidad Javeriana*.

Bernal, G. & De Witte, K. (2026). Student Performance Following the Conversion of Single-Sex Schools to Coeducation: Evidence from Colombia. *Oxford Review of Education*. In Press.

**Funded by
the European Union**

BRIDGE is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101177154). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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